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FACTORS AND PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING INVESTMENT IN THE GREEN ECONOMY

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Annotation:

This article analyzes the essence of the green economy concept, the necessity of attracting investments to it, the key factors affecting the volume of green investments, and future prospects. Based on global experience, effective methods of financing the green economy and proposals for its development in Uzbekistan are developed.

Keywords:

green economy, sustainable development, ecological investment, innovation, sources of financing, carbon neutrality, economic growth.

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Introduction

Global climate change, environmental pollution, and the limited availability of natural resources are prompting a rethinking of modern economic models. In this context, the concept of a green economy—an ecologically clean and socially fair economic model—is becoming increasingly relevant. Investments play a crucial role in implementing this model, as large financial resources are required for technological change, infrastructure modernization, and increasing energy efficiency.

Over the past decades, there has been growing demand for reforming traditional economic models to solve climate change, biodiversity loss, water scarcity, and at the same time, address key social and economic challenges. The global financial crisis of 2008–2009 intensified these discussions, [1] resulting in the emergence of the concept of green transformation of the economy [2,3,4]. The green economy offers an alternative that ensures economic growth and social well-being through a transition to more efficient [5], environmentally friendly, and resource-saving technologies that reduce emissions and mitigate climate change, as well as address the challenges of resource depletion and biosphere degradation. One of the essential components of a green economy strategy is contributing to the achievement of sustainable development goals.

Literature Review

Studies on green economics (UNEP, 2011[7]; OECD, 2020[8]) have substantiated the role of this model in harmonizing economic growth and environmental sustainability. Scholars such as Paul Romer (1990) [10] and Nicholas Stern (2006) [9] consider environmental investment to be the key to long-term economic growth. Uzbek economists Bobokulov S.B., Ismailov K.B., Barotov A.K. (2024) [11] however, argue that

the introduction of green technology has a positive impact on productivity. The World Bank and UNDP reports, on the other hand, point to public and private sector cooperation as the most effective way to attract investment to the green economy.

Research Methodology

This study employs comparative analysis, statistical methods, and a systematic approach. The main sources of data are recent reports from the World Bank, UNDP, the International Energy Agency (IEA), and the State Committee of Statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The correlation between investment flows and green economy indicators was analyzed.

Analysis and Results

In recent years, global investment in the green economy has increased. For example, in 2022, over \$500 billion was allocated to the global renewable energy sector. In contrast, in Uzbekistan, the share of green investments in total domestic investment remains low—around 3-4%.

Key limiting factors include:

- High initial costs of green technologies
- Uncertainty in the investment environment
- Limited financing mechanisms
- Lack of state guarantees
- Inconsistencies in legislation

Promising areas include: solar and wind energy, waste recycling, green transport, and eco-friendly construction. For instance, solar power plant investments are being made in the Nurafshon and Navoi regions.

On November 21, 2023, World Bank representatives presented Uzbekistan's Climate and Development Country Report in Tashkent. The report emphasizes the crucial role of the private sector in Uzbekistan's transition to a green economy and highlights that local firms are more active in green sectors compared to neighboring countries. By

2019, nearly 90% of firms had undertaken green investments, and around 80% conducted green monitoring. However, only 10% considered environmental concerns in business planning, and just 8% explicitly defined their role in addressing these issues.

To encourage green transition, the World Bank recommends reducing the state's role in the economy. Among the key barriers to doing business in Uzbekistan are unreliable electricity access, tax rates, and the informal economy. A transition to clean energy could improve the business environment.

The World Bank also stresses the importance of increasing foreign direct investment (FDI) to develop low-carbon industries. Currently, due to state dominance and weak competition, Uzbekistan lags in attracting investments into green sectors.

Transparency, regulatory stability, strong property rights, coordinated public systems, and efficient investor services are key to attracting FDI, according to the report.

From 2003–2019, half of all FDI went to coal, oil, and gas, while only 5% went to renewable energy. Accelerated trade integration can help local firms enter external markets under green transition conditions. Uzbekistan faces high trade costs, poor logistics, and delays due to trade regulations.

Despite significant tariff reductions, Uzbekistan still has among the highest tariffs in the region. Easing these restrictions could enable firms to access larger markets, boosting growth and job creation.

The World Bank also notes Uzbekistan's high potential for increasing green exports. The country could achieve \$2 billion in green exports, equal to 10% of its exports to Europe and Central Asia, particularly in supplying machinery and electrical equipment for environmental purposes.

On November 15, 2024, during COP-29, the Ministry of Economy and Finance of Uzbekistan met with Helena McLeod, Deputy Director General of the Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI), to discuss joint initiatives, including the project “*Supporting Uzbekistan's Implementation of the Paris Agreement and Cooperation under Article 6 with the Republic of Korea.*” The agreement, worth \$6.5 million in grant funding, aims to assist in implementing green economy reforms and mobilizing green investments, particularly in climate-smart agriculture and forestry, green finance, and carbon markets.

The GGGI Country Partnership Program for Uzbekistan (2024–2028) focuses on:

1. Mobilizing green investments and improving access to sustainable finance in priority sectors;
2. Supporting climate action and green recovery in the Aral Sea region;
3. Promoting climate-smart agriculture and forestry;
4. Enhancing energy efficiency, green technologies in construction and industry, and green urbanization;
5. Supporting legal and institutional frameworks for carbon market development.

Objectives of the joint project with Korea include:

- Building cooperation between Uzbekistan and Korea under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement to reduce GHG emissions through sectoral assessments and action planning;
- Enhancing institutional capacity in climate finance, monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV), and climate adaptation;
- Implementing strategic environmental assessments, green finance mechanisms, and carbon market initiatives.

This agreement creates the foundation for long-term cooperation between the Ministry of Economy and Finance and GGGI.

In addition, the Uzbek Ministry signed a €3 million grant agreement with GIZ under the project "Support to the Private Sector and Economic Policy in Uzbekistan." [6]

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following measures are recommended to increase investment in the green economy:

1. Expand green financing mechanisms – introduce green bonds, subsidies, and tax incentives.
2. Encourage private sector participation – support projects through public-private partnerships.
3. Reduce financial risks – offer guarantees and insurance mechanisms for investors.
4. Enhance human capital – strengthen training and education in green economy disciplines.
5. Improve green regulatory frameworks – harmonize and simplify legal foundations for green development.

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